

RECENT ADVANCES IN UNDERSTANDING PERIODONTITIS PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

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Annotation. The emergence of new technologies, particularly in the fields of genomics, proteomics, and metabolomics, has provided unprecedented insights into the intricate mechanisms underlying periodontal tissue destruction. These technological advances have enabled researchers to identify novel pathogenic pathways, potential therapeutic targets, and biomarkers for early disease detection. Furthermore, the recognition of periodontitis as a dysbiotic disease rather than a classical infectious disease has fundamentally changed our approach to understanding its etiology and progression.

Key words: stomatology, periodontics, periodontium, periodontal diseases, pathology, etiology, pathogenesis, etiopathogenesis.

Introduction. The last decade has witnessed unprecedented advances in our understanding of periodontitis pathophysiology, fundamentally transforming our perspective on this complex inflammatory disease. Recent epidemiological data indicate that severe periodontitis affects approximately 796 million people worldwide, making it the sixth most prevalent human disease. These statistics, coupled with emerging evidence of periodontitis's systemic implications, underscore the critical importance of understanding its underlying pathophysiological mechanisms.

Revolutionary developments in research methodologies, particularly in multi-omics approaches, have provided remarkable insights into the intricate molecular and cellular mechanisms driving periodontal disease progression. High-throughput sequencing technologies, advanced proteomics, and sophisticated bioinformatics tools have revealed previously unknown aspects of host-microbe interactions and inflammatory cascades. The application of single-cell RNA sequencing and spatial transcriptomics has particularly illuminated the complex cellular heterogeneity within periodontal tissues and the dynamic nature of immune responses during disease progression.

Recent research has dramatically shifted our understanding from the traditional bacterial plaque-centered model to a more nuanced perspective of periodontitis as a dysbiosis-driven inflammatory disease. The discovery of keystone pathogens and their role in manipulating the host immune response has revolutionized our comprehension of disease initiation and progression. Modern studies have demonstrated that periodontal tissue destruction results from a complex interplay between dysbiotic microbial communities and aberrant host immune responses, rather than direct bacterial action alone.

Significant breakthroughs in immunology have revealed novel inflammatory mediators and signaling pathways crucial to periodontal pathogenesis. The identification of new subset of immune cells, including tissue-resident memory T cells and innate lymphoid cells, has provided fresh insights into the local immune response in periodontal tissues. Furthermore, the

recognition of trained immunity's role in periodontal disease has opened new avenues for therapeutic intervention.

The advent of advanced imaging techniques, including intravital microscopy and novel molecular imaging probes, has enabled real-time visualization of cellular interactions and inflammatory processes within periodontal tissues. These technological advances have provided unprecedented views of disease progression at the cellular and molecular levels, offering new perspectives on the dynamic nature of periodontal pathophysiology.

Recent investigations have also unveiled the critical role of epigenetic modifications in periodontal disease susceptibility and progression. Studies utilizing cutting-edge epigenomic profiling techniques have identified specific epigenetic signatures associated with different stages of periodontitis, suggesting potential therapeutic targets and biomarkers for disease monitoring.

The emergence of artificial intelligence and machine learning applications in periodontal research has facilitated the integration of complex datasets, leading to the identification of novel pathophysiological patterns and potential therapeutic targets. These computational approaches have enabled researchers to analyze vast amounts of molecular and clinical data, revealing previously unrecognized disease mechanisms and progression patterns.

Understanding the bidirectional relationship between periodontitis and systemic conditions has emerged as a crucial area of research. Recent studies have demonstrated that periodontal inflammation can significantly impact systemic health through various mechanisms, including the release of inflammatory mediators, bacterial translocation, and immune system modulation. This knowledge has important implications for both dental and medical practice.

Modern research has also highlighted the role of the periodontal microenvironment in disease progression, including the importance of metabolic alterations, oxidative stress, and tissue repair mechanisms. Advanced metabolomic studies have revealed specific metabolic signatures associated with disease progression, providing new insights into potential therapeutic interventions.

The integration of these recent advances has led to a more comprehensive understanding of periodontitis pathophysiology, enabling the development of novel therapeutic strategies and personalized treatment approaches. This review aims to synthesize these recent discoveries, focusing on their implications for clinical practice and future research directions in periodontal medicine.

By examining these recent advances in understanding periodontitis pathophysiology, we can better appreciate the complexity of this disease and develop more effective strategies for its prevention and treatment. This knowledge is essential for advancing both basic research and clinical practice in periodontal medicine, ultimately leading to improved patient outcomes.

References:

1. Bulkina, N. V. Comorbidity of periodontal diseases and somatic pathology / N. V. Bulkina, A.V. Vedyayeva, E. A. Savina // Medical Bulletin of the North Caucasus. - 2012. - No. 3. - URL: <http://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/komorbidnost-zabolev> (date of application: 02/19/2017).

2. Risovanny, S. I. Functional assessment of the state of microcirculation in high-intensity laser therapy of chronic periodontitis / S. I. Risovanny // Russian Dental Journal. - 2001. - No. 5. - pp. 13-18.
3. Ulitovsky, S. B. The role of oral hygiene in the development of periodontal diseases / S. B. Ulitovsky // Periodontology. - 2000. - No. 3. - pp. 34-36.
4. Balashov, A. N. Possibilities of using the theory of mass service in the organization of intensive admission of dental patients / A. N. Balashov // Dentistry. - 1999. - No. 1. - pp. 62-63.